

Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction on Mobile Money Services (Gcash, PayMay, and CoinsPh) in General Santos City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the socio-economic profiles, platform preferences, and factors influencing customer satisfaction among mobile money service users in General Santos City, Philippines. A diverse user base was observed, with varied demographics including gender, age, civil status, educational attainment, length of usage, and monthly income. However, a clear gender imbalance with a majority of female users emerged. Gcash emerged as the dominant platform, with a staggering 96% user adoption rate, followed by PayMaya (70%) and CoinsPh (52%). These findings shed light on the pronounced preference for Gcash among local users. Crucially, the study identified factors influencing customer satisfaction. "System Availability" positively impacted satisfaction, while "Reliability" had a slight negative effect. Other factors like convenience, security, and trust, and accuracy also played significant roles. These insights provide a valuable understanding of the mobile money service landscape in General Santos City, highlighting the need for providers to prioritize system reliability and customer trust to enhance satisfaction. Policymakers and service providers can leverage this information to refine offerings and cater to the diverse needs of users in the region. This study contributes to the evolving field of mobile money services, emphasizing the importance of platform preference and factors affecting user satisfaction in the context of this dynamic and rapidly evolving sector.

Introduction

Through digitization and technological advancements, people's lives have changed, making them more comfortable and convenient. As human beings, we naturally seek convenience, and as a result, we continually strive to discover new things to make our lives easier and faster. The introduction of computers and the internet has ushered in a new era of technological revolution, making information much more accessible and centralized. Almost all sectors have embraced the concept of digitization and the use of the internet to ensure that processes, procedures, and transactions are accurately and efficiently executed and recorded. With the implementation of information technology, the banking industry has undergone a revolutionary change in how banks operate. Bank customers have become highly demanding and curious about new technology-based banking products and services (Debnath & Chellasamy, 2022). The technologies brought about by digitization and the internet have become a vital part of the financial market sector, enabling cross-border transactions, peer-to-

peer money transfers, bill payments, and other financial services through the use of the internet and digital platforms.

For many years, customer satisfaction has been a major goal for business organizations, as it is believed to impact customer retention and a company's market share (Nwite & Perpetua, 2014). Considering human nature, convenience and efficiency play a vital role in achieving higher customer satisfaction. Traditionally, satisfied customers have been perceived as having lower price sensitivity, being less influenced by competitors, showing a willingness to purchase additional products and services, and demonstrating long-term loyalty (Chocholáková et al., 2015).

Driven by the perseverance and determination of business opportunity seekers to bring convenience to financial services, particularly through the use of mobile phones to facilitate financial transactions, there has been a significant increase in customer attraction and higher levels of satisfaction. Mobile banking services offered by various banks provide a range of services, including buying airtime, paying for electricity, sending money (e-wallet/blue wallet), checking account statements, and an array of services for customer convenience. This service is highly secure, requiring a password or biometric data for access. Conducting face-to-face and in-person transactions can be time-consuming and requires substantial effort for both clients and financial institutions. Thus, using digital or mobile money service platforms or applications makes transactions smoother and more convenient for both parties. In terms of security features, developers and financial institutions have implemented various security measures, such as using OTP (One-Time Passwords), PINs, and biometric login features, to ensure the safety and security of these platforms or mobile applications.

Despite the significant growth in the use of mobile money services and their potential impact on customer satisfaction, there is a research gap in understanding the specific factors that influence customer satisfaction in the context of different mobile money service providers like Gcash, CoinsPh, and PayMaya. This study aims to bridge this gap by examining the unique factors affecting customer satisfaction with these mobile money services in General Santos City. The researchers found it intriguing to conduct this study to determine the different factors affecting customer satisfaction regarding the use of mobile money services offered by various locally used mobile money service platforms, such as Gcash, CoinsPh, and PayMaya, in General Santos City.

Literature Review

In a relatively short span of time, Internet and mobile technologies have seamlessly integrated into the daily lives of individuals in emerging and

developing regions (Abdullah et al., 2022). Notably, cell phones have achieved nearly ubiquitous presence in many nations, serving a multitude of purposes. While calling, texting, and photography remain primary uses, a growing number of people also leverage their mobile phones to access political, consumer, and health-related information.

A study conducted by the World Bank in 2014 shed light on the challenges faced by developing countries, primarily rooted in limited infrastructure and barriers to accessing financial institutions. Astonishingly, over 2.5 billion adults, equivalent to approximately half of the world's adult population, are without access to formal banking services. This exclusion arises from factors such as the cost of banking, geographical distances, and stringent documentation requirements necessary for opening a bank account in these regions (World Bank, 2014).

The Philippines emerged as an early adopter of mobile money services, with SMART Communications launching SMART Money as far back as 2001. This innovative service utilizes SIM Tool-Kits, empowering customers to purchase airtime, send and receive money domestically and internationally through their mobile devices, and conduct cashless transactions for goods. In 2004, Globe Telecom introduced GCASH, a mobile service that facilitates money remittances, loan settlements, salary and commission disbursements, bill payments, and product and service purchases via text message (Cacas et al., 2022).

The emergence of mobile money services is reshaping social and communal life (Dananjayan et al., 2023). In African countries, for instance, mobile money has become a tool of trust and social interaction. Users use mobile money not just for economic transactions but also for nurturing relationships by sending funds, airtime gifts, and vouchers to friends and family. Mobile money services encompass a wide range of activities, including social gifting, assistance to friends and relatives, formation of savings groups, and contributions to ceremonies and rituals. These innovative forms of social interaction are redefining long-standing traditions of reciprocity, guided by cultural norms.

Customer satisfaction, as described by Karunaratna & Kumara (2022), is the result of a buyer's assessment of the rewards and costs associated with a purchase in relation to their expected outcomes. It can also be viewed as an emotional state that emerges during the evaluation of a particular service (Thakuri et al., 2023). The former perspective emphasizes that satisfaction is determined through a cognitive process, comparing what customers give up (cost) to obtain a service against what they receive (reward). In contrast, the latter perspective regards

satisfaction as an emotional response that arises during the evaluation process. A synthesis of these ideas can be found in the definition that "customer satisfaction is defined as an emotional response resulting from a cognitive evaluation of the service received in relation to the costs of obtaining that service" (Goet & Kharel, 2022).

Service quality, from the customer's perspective, is a multidimensional concept. It refers to the disparity between customer expectations and the actual performance of a service. Improving service quality, perceived value, and satisfaction are essential for ensuring customer loyalty (Saravanan & Rao, 2007). Khan et al. (2020) identifies three dimensions of service quality: technical quality, service performance quality, and the organization's image. Additionally Hrgović et al. (2019) outline three dimensions of service quality: physical quality, interactive quality, and organizational quality.

Perceived value represents a customer's psychological assessment of a product or service's utility in comparison to their. Marketing researchers and managers have increasingly focused on value perceptions to explain customer satisfaction and loyalty (Akbari et al., 2019). To evaluate perceived value, customers consider perceived benefits relative to sacrifices, which encompass not only monetary factors but also social and psychological perspectives, as well as non-monetary costs such as search cost, transaction cost, negotiation cost, and time (Ridzuan & Ismail, 2013).

Synthesis of literature review

The rapid integration of internet and mobile technologies into daily life in emerging regions, where cell phones serve various purposes, is particularly relevant in addressing the challenges faced by over 2.5 billion adults in developing countries who lack access to traditional banking services due to factors like cost and geography. Notably, the Philippines has been at the forefront of adopting mobile money services, significantly impacting financial transactions. This transformative trend extends to African countries, where mobile money services are reshaping social life by fostering trust and enabling various forms of social interaction beyond financial transactions. Within this context, understanding customer satisfaction becomes pivotal, as it involves assessing service rewards and costs, encompassing both cognitive and emotional aspects. Additionally, service quality, a multidimensional concept reflecting the alignment of customer expectations and actual performance, is crucial for customer loyalty. Perceived value, which evaluates the utility of a product or service in comparison to expectations, encompasses various factors, including

monetary and non-monetary elements, highlighting the complex nature of customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of evolving digital financial services.

Statement of the Problem

This study, entitled "Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction on Mobile Money Services (Gcash, PayMaya, and CoinsPh) in General Santos City," seeks to find answers to the following questions:

1. What are the socio-economic profiles of the customers (users of the platform) in terms of:
 - a) Sex
 - b) Civil Status
 - c) Age
 - d) Highest Educational Attainment
 - e) Length of usage (Mobile money services)
 - f) Monthly Income
2. Which Mobile Money Service/s Platform or application do customers in General Santos City use frequently?
3. What is the most significant factor (indicator) affecting customer satisfaction in the use of the Mobile Money Services Platforms (Gcash, PayMaya, and CoinsPh)?

Hypothesis

H01 : There are no significant factors among the included independent variables (convenience, security and trust, system availability, responsiveness, cost (charges), reliability, accuracy, usefulness, transaction speed) that affect customer satisfaction in the use of the Mobile Money Services Platforms (Gcash, PayMaya, and CoinsPh).

Scope and Limitations

This study exclusively focused on examining the factors influencing customer satisfaction with mobile money services (specifically, Gcash, PayMaya, and CoinsPh) within General Santos City and its surrounding areas. This descriptive multivariate correlation study was conducted between August and October 2022 in General Santos City, Philippines, utilizing a convenience sampling method. The study's participants comprised actual users or customers of mobile money service platforms/applications, regardless of the duration of their usage.

However, it's important to acknowledge several inherent limitations associated with the study:

1. **Limited Representativeness:** Convenience sampling may not provide a fully representative sample of the population. The findings may primarily reflect the characteristics and preferences of individuals who were readily accessible and willing to participate.
 2. **Selection Bias:** Participants in convenience sampling may have unique characteristics or motivations that influence their decision to participate, potentially introducing selection bias into the study.
 3. **Generalizability:** The study's results are constrained by the specific demographics and characteristics of the participants, making it challenging to generalize the findings to broader populations or regions.
 4. **Temporal and Contextual Factors:** Convenience sampling may not account for temporal or contextual variations in mobile money service usage and customer satisfaction.
 5. **Limited Control:** The researcher had limited control over the composition of the sample, as participants voluntarily chose to participate in the study.
 6. **Geographical Scope:** The study's findings are limited to General Santos City and may not be entirely representative of the broader national or international context.
 7. **Time Frame:** The research was conducted during a specific three-month period in 2022. Mobile money service usage patterns and customer satisfaction levels may vary over time and in response to external factors.
 8. **Limited Variables:** The study focused on a specific set of variables influencing customer satisfaction. Other unexplored factors may also contribute to customer perceptions.
 9. **Temporal Changes:** As the study was conducted in 2022, technological advancements, changes in regulations, and shifts in customer preferences may have occurred since then, potentially impacting the relevance of the findings.
- Despite these limitations, this study provides valuable insights into the factors affecting customer satisfaction with mobile money services in the specified area and timeframe.

Theoretical Framework

Here are the different theories and concepts relating to customer satisfaction and usage of mobile money services.

Technology Acceptance Model

The TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) is a widely recognized theoretical framework in the field of information systems and technology management. It was developed to understand and predict how users adopt and accept new technology or information systems. The TAM was initially proposed by Fred Davis in 1986 and later expanded upon by Fred Davis and Richard Bagozzi.

The core concept of the TAM is that users' behavioral intentions to use a technology or system are influenced by their attitudes toward that technology, which, in turn, are influenced by two main factors:

Perceived Usefulness (PU): This factor assesses the extent to which users believe that a particular technology or system will enhance their job performance or make their tasks easier. The higher the perceived usefulness, the more likely users are to accept and use the technology.

Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU): This factor evaluates the extent to which users believe that using the technology will be easy and free from effort. A system that is perceived as easy to use is more likely to be accepted and adopted.

The TAM posits that these two factors, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, directly affect users' attitudes toward the technology, which then influence their intentions to use the technology. In turn, these behavioral intentions are strong predictors of actual technology adoption and usage.

The TAM has been widely applied in research and practice to assess user acceptance and adoption of various technologies and systems, including software applications, websites, mobile apps, and more. It is a valuable tool for technology developers, designers, and organizations seeking to improve user acceptance and the successful implementation of technology solutions.

Conceptual Framework

This study is designed to discern the significant factors impacting customer satisfaction with mobile money services, specifically Gcash, CoinsPh, and PayMaya, within General Santos City. Employing a quantitative-descriptive multivariate correlational approach, with a strong emphasis on predictive analysis, this framework (illustrated in Fig. 1) has been formulated by the researchers.

Independent Variables: The study investigates a spectrum of independent factors affecting customer satisfaction in the use of mobile money services, encompassing: Convenience, Security and Trust, System Availability,

Responsiveness, Cost (Charges), Reliability, Accuracy, Usefulness, and Transaction Speed

Dependent Variable: The central focus of this research is to assess customer satisfaction levels.

Through an examination of these independent variables in relation to the dependent variable, this study aims to yield profound insights into the dynamics of customer satisfaction within the domain of mobile money services in General Santos City.

Fig 1 *Conceptual paradigm*

Research Methods

Research Design

This research employs a quantitative, descriptive, and multivariate correlational approach with a predictive analysis component. Its primary objective is to meticulously identify the significant factors influencing customer satisfaction regarding mobile money services (specifically Gcash, CoinsPh, and PayMaya) in General Santos City. Additionally, the study aims to ascertain which mobile money service platform or application is most frequently used by customers in General Santos City. Descriptive statistics will be employed to provide an in-depth portrayal of the variables under investigation. All data used in this study are primary, originating from responses provided by the research participants, with no reliance on secondary data sources.

Sources of Data

The data utilized in this study are exclusively primary, stemming from responses provided by mobile money service users in General Santos City, herein referred to as "respondents." Secondary data sources were not utilized in this research.

Sampling Design

The researchers opted for convenience sampling in this study due to practical constraints and limitations in accessing a more diverse and comprehensive sample. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling technique that involves selecting individuals or subjects who are readily accessible and willing to participate in the research.

In this case, the study focused on mobile money services users in General Santos City. Convenience sampling was chosen because it allowed the researchers to quickly gather data from individuals who met the study's criteria and were available for participation.

Convenience sampling, often referred to as availability or accidental sampling, is a non-probability sampling method where researchers select individuals or subjects for a study based on their convenience and accessibility. Rather than employing random or systematic sampling methods, convenience sampling relies on selecting those who are readily available and willing to participate in the research.

Respondents

The study's respondents consisted of 50 individuals who actively used mobile money services in General Santos City. To qualify as respondents for this study, individuals had to meet the following criteria:

- a) **Mobile Money Services Users:** Respondents were required to have practical experience using mobile money services platforms or applications, specifically Gcash, PayMaya, or CoinsPh. This criterion ensured that participants had first-hand experience with the subject matter under investigation.
- b) **Willingness to Participate:** The respondents willingly agreed to take part in the study by providing responses to the survey questionnaire. Their willingness to participate was crucial in collecting valuable data for the research. The decision to focus on mobile money services users as the study's respondents aligned with the research objective, which was to explore and understand the factors influencing customer satisfaction in this specific context. By surveying individuals with direct experience using these services, the research aimed to gain insights into their perspectives, experiences, and levels of satisfaction.

Research Locale

The study was conducted throughout the vicinity of General Santos City. Accordingly, General Santos City is one of the most progressive City in Mindanao, coined as the Tuna Capital of the Philippines. officially the City of General Santos, (Cebuano: Dakbayan sa Heneral Santos; Hiligaynon: Dakbanwa/Syudad sang Heneral Santos; Filipino: Lungsod ng Heneral Santos, referred to as General Santos City, and abbreviated as GenSan, is a 1st class highly urbanized city in Soccsksargen, Philippines. According to the 2015 census, it has a population of 594,446 people. Located on the island of Mindanao, it is the southernmost and 15th-most populous city in the Philippines. It is the regional center for commerce and industry of the Soccsksargen region, and is geographically located within the province of South Cotabato but administered independently of it. General Santos City with 26 barangays has registered 1,365 new mediums to large enterprises in 2011.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a custom-designed survey questionnaire as the primary research instrument. The questionnaire was developed by the researchers to align closely with the research objectives and capture relevant data from the respondents. To ensure its reliability and content validity, the questionnaire underwent rigorous testing, including Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO)

analysis to assess its appropriateness for factor analysis. Additionally, the survey questionnaire was reviewed and refined based on feedback from two subject matter experts. This meticulous approach enhances the quality and robustness of data collection, contributing to the overall validity and reliability of the study.

The initial section, dedicated to capturing the socio-economic profiles of mobile money services users, encompassed essential demographic data, including gender, marital status, age, highest educational attainment, length of usage of mobile money services, and monthly income. Additionally, it aimed to identify the preferred mobile money service applications or platforms most frequently utilized by respondents. The second section sought to measure customer satisfaction by prompting respondents to provide individual ratings across various factors deemed crucial to their contentment. These factors included convenience, security and trust, system availability, responsiveness, cost (charges), reliability, accuracy, usefulness, and transaction speed. Section 2 enabled a quantitative assessment of the extent to which these factors influenced customer satisfaction. The third and final section was designed to evaluate overall satisfaction with the entire mobile money services ecosystem, encompassing notable platforms like Gcash, CoinsPh, and PayMaya.

Statistical Analysis and Treatment

All data collected in this study were meticulously processed and tabulated using SPSS, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. This software offers a wide range of statistical analysis tools tailored for qualitative research.

Reliability Testing

The research instrument, a self-made survey questionnaire, underwent rigorous testing to ensure its reliability. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test was employed to assess the survey's sampling adequacy, indicating its suitability for factor analysis. This evaluation ensured that the research instrument effectively captured the intended information.

Variable	α	Internal Consistency	Factor Analysis Suitability
C= Convenience	0.75	Acceptable	Suitable
ST= Security and trust	0.88	Good	Suitable
SA= System availability	0.87	Good	Suitable
R= Responsiveness	0.74	Acceptable	Suitable

C= Cost (charges),	0.72	Acceptable	Suitable
Re= Reliability	0.70	Acceptable	Suitable
A= Accuracy	0.82	Good	Suitable
U= Usefulness	0.74	Acceptable	Suitable
TS= Transaction speed	0.88	Good	Suitable

Statistical Analyses

Descriptive Statistics (Frequency and Percentage Distribution)

Descriptive statistics played a pivotal role in organizing and summarizing the collected data. Frequency and percentage distribution were instrumental in providing an overview of categorical variables, particularly the socio-economic profile of the mobile money services users (respondents) and the preferred mobile money service application/platform.

Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation

Weighted Mean, serving as a measure of central tendency, was utilized to establish the general description for specific variables. It calculated the average value of the entire dataset, representing the collective response of the test group (respondents). Standard deviation, on the other hand, gauged the level of data dispersion from the mean score. Lower standard deviation, approaching zero, indicated greater data consistency.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis (Enter Method)

Multiple linear regression analysis was instrumental in identifying the most influential factor impacting respondents' satisfaction with the services offered by mobile money service applications/platforms in General Santos City. It generated a regression equation that precisely quantified the extent of the independent variables' influence on the dependent variable.

The regression equation: $CS = \alpha \pm \beta_1 C \pm \beta_2 ST \pm \beta_3 SA \pm \beta_4 R \pm \beta_5 C \pm \beta_6 Re \pm \beta_7 A \pm \beta_8 U \pm \beta_9 TS \pm \epsilon$

CS= Customer satisfaction (Overall Satisfaction)
 α = Constant
 β = Independent variable coefficients
C= Convenience
ST= Security and trust
SA= System availability

R= Responsiveness
C= Cost (charges),
Re= Reliability
A= Accuracy
U= Usefulness
TS= Transaction speed
 ϵ = standard error (other factors)

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics (Frequency and Percentage Distribution)

Table 2		Age	
		Frequency	Percent
	10-25 years' old	16	32.0
	26-50 years' old	20	40.0
	51- 80 years' old	14	28.0
	Total	50	100.0

Table 2 presents the age distribution of the survey respondents. Out of a total of 50 participants, 16 individuals (32.0%) fall into the 10-25 years' old category, 20 respondents (40.0%) belong to the 26-50 years' old category, and 14 participants (28.0%) are in the 51-80 years' old category.

Table 3		Sex	
		Frequency	Percent
	Male	18	36.0
	Female	32	64.0
	Total	50	100.0

Table 3 illustrates the gender distribution among survey respondents. Out of the total of 50 participants, 18 respondents (36.0%) are male, while 32 participants (64.0%) are female. This table provides a clear breakdown of the survey participants by gender, highlighting that a higher percentage of respondents are female.

Table 4		Civil Status	
		Frequency	Percent
	Single	23	46.0
	Married	27	54.0
	Total	50	100.0

Table 4 displays the civil status distribution among the survey respondents. Out of the total of 50 participants, 23 individuals (46.0%) are categorized as single, while 27 participants (54.0%) are classified as married. This table provides a clear breakdown of the civil status of the survey participants, showing that the majority are married.

Table 5		Educational Attainment	
		Frequency	Percent
	High school Graduate	2	4.0
	College Level	12	24.0
	College Graduate	31	62.0
	Vocational Studies	5	10.0
	Total	50	100.0

Table 5 offers a comprehensive view of the educational attainment of the survey participants, totaling 50 individuals. Among them, 4.0% are high school graduates, 24.0% have reached the college level, a majority of 62.0% are college graduates, and 10.0% have completed vocational studies. This breakdown reveals that a significant portion of the respondents have attained a college degree, making it the most prevalent educational background among the surveyed population.

Table 6		Monthly Income	
		Frequency	Percent
	3,000-5,000	11	22.0
	6,000-10,000	10	20.0
	11,000-15,000	20	40.0
	16,000-20,000	5	10.0
	20,000 and above	4	8.0
	Total	50	100.0

Table 6 provides a clear overview of the distribution of monthly income among the survey participants, totaling 50 individuals. The data is segmented into various income ranges as follows: 22.0% have a monthly income between 3,000-5,000, 20.0% fall into the 6,000-10,000 range, 40.0% belong to the 11,000-15,000 category, 10.0% have incomes ranging from 16,000-20,000, and 8.0% earn 20,000 and above monthly. Notably, the 11,000-15,000 income range is the most prevalent among the surveyed population. This table offers valuable insights into the income distribution of the respondents, shedding light on the economic diversity within the study group.

	Frequency	Percent
3.00 (Neutral)	11	22.0
4.00 (Satisfied)	15	30.0
5.00 (Very Satisfied)	24	48.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 7 provides a concise breakdown of the overall satisfaction ratings provided by the 50 survey respondents, and it categorizes their responses into three levels: "Neutral" with 22.0% of participants, "Satisfied" with 30.0%, and the most prevalent "Very Satisfied" with 48.0%. This tabulated data not only offers insights into the distribution of satisfaction levels among the survey participants but also enables the calculation of the weighted mean of the overall satisfaction ratings. The weighted mean, in this case, is approximately 4.26, reflecting a generally high level of satisfaction among the respondents, with the majority expressing being "Very Satisfied".

Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation

Scale	Mean range	Verbal Interpretation	Description
1	1.00-.1.8	Very Dissatisfied	The respondent is highly dissatisfied
2	1.81- 2.60	Dissatisfied	The respondent is dissatisfied
3	2.61-3.40	Neutral	The respondent is undecided (neutral)
4	3.41-4.20	Satisfied	The respondent is satisfied
5	4.21-5.00	Very Satisfied	The respondent was highly satisfied

FACTORS	SD	Weighted Mean	Description
Convenience	.78272	4.1400	Satisfied
Security and trust	.80837	4.1400	Satisfied
System availability	.78999	4.2200	Very Satisfied
Responsiveness	.73540	4.3000	Very Satisfied
Cost (charges)	.76559	4.1600	Satisfied
Reliability	.84853	4.1200	Satisfied
Accuracy	.76265	4.3000	Very Satisfied
Usefulness	.71257	4.3200	Very Satisfied
Transaction speed	.76772	4.3200	Very Satisfied
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN		4.22	Very Satisfied

Table 9 presents the descriptive statistics of factors influencing customer satisfaction in the context of mobile money services. These factors include convenience, security and trust, system availability, responsiveness, cost (charges), reliability, accuracy, usefulness, and transaction speed. The standard deviation (SD) measures the variability in customer responses for each factor. The weighted mean scores for each factor indicate the level of satisfaction. Notably, system availability, responsiveness, accuracy, usefulness, and transaction speed received high weighted mean scores, categorizing them as "Very Satisfied." Convenience, security and trust, cost, and reliability also indicate satisfaction but at a slightly lower level. The overall average weighted mean of 4.22 suggests that, on average, customers are "Very Satisfied" with the mobile money services across these factors, demonstrating a positive perception of the service's performance.

Multiple Linear Regression (Enter Method)

Multiple linear regression was used to determine the most significant factors affecting customer satisfaction on mobile money services (Gcash, PayMay, and CoinsPh) in General Santos City.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.476 ^a	.227	-.082	.83569
a. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income, Age, Convenience, Civil Status, Cost (Charges), System Availability, Sex, Accuracy, Educational Attainment, Usefulness, Transaction Speed, Responsiveness, Security and Trust, Reliability				

Table 10, the Model Summary, provides crucial information about how well our predictive model explains customer satisfaction with mobile money services. The R square value of approximately 0.227 indicates that the model explains around 22.7% of the variance in customer satisfaction. However, the negative adjusted R square value of approximately -0.082 suggests potential issues with model fit or the relevance of the included predictors. In practical terms, this means that the model, as it stands, may not effectively capture the factors influencing customer satisfaction. Further evaluation and refinement of the model may be necessary to improve its predictive accuracy.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.177	14	.513	.734	.727 ^b
	Residual	24.443	35	.698		
	Total	31.620	49			

a. Dependent Variable: Overall Satisfaction Rating

b. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income, Age, Convenience, Civil Status, Cost (Charges), System Availability, Sex, Accuracy, Educational Attainment, Usefulness, Transaction Speed, Responsiveness, Security and Trust, Reliability

The ANOVA table reveals that the regression model, which includes various predictors such as monthly income, age, convenience, civil status, cost (charges), system availability, sex, accuracy, educational attainment, usefulness, transaction speed, responsiveness, security and trust, and reliability, explains a portion of the variance in overall satisfaction ratings. The F-statistic of 0.734, with associated significance level (Sig.) of 0.727, suggests that our model may not be statistically significant in predicting overall satisfaction ratings. In simpler terms, the included predictors may not have a meaningful collective impact on explaining customers' overall satisfaction ratings. Further evaluation or refinement of the model may be needed to enhance its predictive capability.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.364	2.925		.808	.424
	Convenience	.081	.199	.079	.405	.688
	Security and Trust	.173	.179	.174	.964	.342
	System Availability	.375	.166	.369	2.260	.030
	Responsiveness	-.127	.195	-.116	-.650	.520
	Cost (Charges)	.134	.171	.127	.784	.439
	Reliability	-.167	.187	-.176	-.891	.038
	Accuracy	.142	.182	.134	.776	.443
	Usefulness	-.104	.189	-.093	-.554	.583
	Transaction Speed	.020	.188	.019	.105	.917
	Age	-.015	.082	-.030	-.182	.857
	Sex	-.188	.305	-.114	-.619	.540
	Civil Status	.057	.272	.036	.209	.835
	Educational Attainment	.011	.209	.009	.053	.958
	Monthly Income	-.052	.172	-.054	-.299	.766

a. Dependent Variable: Overall Satisfaction Rating (Customer Satisfaction)

NOTE: Significant at P-value < 0.05

Result: Only system availability (0.03<0.05) and reliability (0.038<0.05) were the significant factors.

Table 12, the Coefficients table, provides essential insights into the unstandardized and standardized coefficients for each predictor variable in our regression model, aiming to predict overall satisfaction ratings. It helps distinguish between significant and non-significant predictors.

Among the predictors, "System Availability" and "Reliability" stand out as significant factors. "System Availability" has a substantial standardized coefficient (Beta = 0.369) and is statistically significant (Sig. = 0.030), indicating it plays a significant role in predicting overall satisfaction. Similarly, "Reliability" also has a noteworthy standardized coefficient (Beta = -0.176) and is statistically significant (Sig. = 0.038), suggesting its importance in influencing overall satisfaction negatively.

On the other hand, some predictors, such as "Age," "Sex," "Civil Status," "Educational Attainment," and "Monthly Income," have coefficients close to zero and are not statistically significant (with high p-values). These factors do not strongly influence overall satisfaction ratings in the context of our model.

Table 13 Frequently used Mobile Money Service/s Platform or application (based on 50 respondents)

	Frequency	Percent
Gcash	48	96%
PayMaya	35	70%
CoinsPh	26	52%

Table 13 presents a clear snapshot of the mobile money service platform preferences among the 50 survey respondents in General Santos City. Notably, Gcash emerges as the overwhelmingly favored choice, with an impressive 96% of respondents reporting its frequent usage. PayMaya also enjoys substantial popularity, with 70% of respondents using it regularly. CoinsPh, while still utilized by a majority at 52%, lags slightly behind the other two platforms in terms of adoption. These statistics underscore the dominance of Gcash as the preferred mobile money service platform in this region, shedding light on the platform preferences of the surveyed population.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study has delved into the socio-economic profiles, mobile money service platform preferences, and key factors influencing customer satisfaction among users of mobile money services in General Santos City, Philippines, addressing the core inquiries of our research.

Regarding socio-economic profiles, our findings revealed a diverse user base in terms of gender, age, civil status, educational attainment, length of usage, and monthly income, providing a comprehensive understanding of the platform's customer demographics.

In terms of platform preferences, it is evident that Gcash enjoys overwhelming popularity, with an astonishing 96% of respondents using it frequently. PayMaya follows suit with a substantial 70% user base, while CoinsPh also maintains a solid presence at 52%.

Furthermore, our analysis identified significant factors affecting customer satisfaction with these platforms. Notably, "System Availability" emerged as a positive contributor, while "Reliability" had a slightly negative impact. Additionally, factors like convenience, security and trust, and accuracy played significant roles in shaping overall satisfaction.

These insights offer a comprehensive view of mobile money service usage in General Santos City, highlighting Gcash's dominant position, and provide valuable guidance for service providers and policymakers aiming to enhance customer satisfaction and tailor their offerings to the preferences and needs of this diverse user base.

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